

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Additional Deliverable AD6.4

Inventory of PBK models for assessing the internal exposure through life

WP 6 – T6.2

Technical reference	
Work package	WP 6 - Innovation in regulatory risk assessment
Task	T 6.2 – Integrative exposure and risk assessment
Dissemination level ¹	PU
Lead Beneficiary/ Responsible AE	INERIS, AUTH
Contributing Participants	ANSES, IISPV, RIVM, SLU, IVL,TNO, VITO, NIPH, IFRMN, WR, ISSeP, ONIRIS, CSIC, OVAM, KWR, WSFR, CSIC-IDAEA, IUSS, RECETOX
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Due date of deliverable	30 April 2023
Actual submission date	27 June 2023

¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/Institutions	Short description of changes
1	28/11/2022	Responsible authors	Add the table of contents and some template by subsection
2	15/03/2023	All authors	First version
3	04/04/2023	ANSES/VITO	Draft version for review by the Reviewers
4	08/05/2023	Sylvia Escher George Kass	Draft version with comments provided by reviewers
5	15/06/2023	Responsible authors	Final version incorporating comments from the reviewers and WP co-leads, for submission to the European Commission
6	19/10/2023	Responsible authors	Final version incorporating comments from the European Commission

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Abstract

Physiologically Based kinetic (PBK or PBPK or PBTK) models are essential tools in toxicokinetic (TK) modelling and risk assessment as they describe the Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion (ADME) processes of chemicals in the human body. Over the past few years, the HBM4EU project has reviewed available PBK models for selected compounds (*e.g.*, PFAS, metals, pesticides), highlighting a lack of TK data for many prioritized compounds and a lack of models for sensitive populations such as pregnant women and fetuses, newborns, young children, or the elderly.

As a first step of this PARC project, the aim of this report is to provide an inventory of PBK models currently available for assessing internal exposure during the life course in considering age dependent variation in organ physiology, metabolism and clearance from *in utero* to end of life. This will allow to provide some recommendations to fill the identified gaps and perspectives on the use of PBK models in risk assessment.

Efforts should be redirected towards the refinement or development of PBK models to address the sensitivities of population sub-groups (including the evolution through life of associated processes), integrating multiple routes and sources of exposure, and to fill the knowledge gaps on the *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation (*e.g.*, quantification of metabolites in liver, kinetic parameters regarding barrier organs, integration of active transport, tiered testing strategies), leading to IVIVE-PBK models.

Key Words

PBK model; Children; Advanced age; Pregnancy; In utero; Inter-individual variability; Prioritized compounds; Data gaps; Exposure assessment; Lifetime exposure; Sensitive populations.

List of abbreviations

α -ZEL: α -Zearalenol

ADME: Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion

AFB1: Aflatoxin B1

AOPs: Adverse Outcome Pathways

As: Arsenic

AUC: Area Under the Curve

BBB: Blood-Brain Barrier

BCRP: Breast Cancer Resistance Protein

BPs: Bisphenols

BPA: Bisphenol A

BPAF: Bisphenol AF

BPB: Bisphenol B

BPE: Bisphenol E

BPF: Bisphenol F

BPP: Bisphenol P

BPS: Bisphenol S

Cd: Cadmium

CPF: Chlorpyrifos

Cr: Chromium

Cr(III): Trivalent Chromium

Cr(VI): Hexavalent Chromium

CYP: Cytochrome P450

DEET: N,N-diethyl-meta-toluamide

DMA: Dimethyl arsenic Acid

DON: Deoxynivalenol

FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

FBs: Fumonisin

GMP: Good Modelling Practices

HBM: Human BioMonitoring

HBM-GV: Human BioMonitoring Guidance Value

HED: human equivalent dose (HED)

Hg: Mercury

iAs: inorganic Arsenic

IATA: Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment

IVIVE: *In Vitro* to *In Vivo* Extrapolation

LC-MS/MS: Liquid Chromatography coupled to tandem Mass Spectrometry

MCMC: Markov Chain Monte Carlo

MMA: MonoMethylarsonic Acid

NAMs: New Approach Methods (or New Alternative Methodologies)

OAT: Organic anion transporter

OCT: Organic cation transporter

OP: Organophosphate

OTA: Ochratoxin A

PAT: Patulin

Pb: Lead

PBK (or PBPK or PBTK): Physiologically Based (Pharmac- or Toxic) Kinetic

p-PBK (or p-PBPK or p-PBTK): Pregnancy-Physiologically Based (Pharmac- or Toxic) Kinetic

P-gp: P-glycoprotein Transporter (OCT).

PC: Partition Coefficient

PFAS: Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl substances

PFHxS: Perfluorohexane sulfonate

PFNA: Perfluorononanoic acid

PFOA: Perfluorooctanoic acid

PFOS: Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid

PoD: Point of Departure

QIVIVE: Quantitative *In Vitro* to *In Vivo* Extrapolation

QSAR: Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship

RA: Risk Assessment

RBC: Red Blood Cell

RfC: Reference Concentration

RfD: Reference Dose

RPF: Relative Potency Factor

SULT: Sulfotransferase

TDI: Tolerable Daily Intake

TK: Toxicokinetic

UGT: Uridine diphospho-glucuronosyltransferase

ZEN: Zearalenone

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1. Context

Humans are daily exposed to numerous substances. Human biomonitoring (HBM) surveys are performed to monitor exposures or early effects related to the presence of substances in the body. HBM surveys consist of sample biological matrices (blood, urine, etc.) to quantify the substances of interest. This measure includes all sources of exposure regardless of the routes of entry of substances into the human body, and regardless of the place of exposure (home, work, etc.), activity or products consumed. Conducted at the scale of a population, HBM campaigns allow: (i) to assess the degree of internal population exposure of substances, (ii) to provide public health factors with information relating to the population exposure of substances, their sources, and the predominant routes of exposure, and (iii) the risk of health effects of the general population linked to population exposure. However, HBM studies only provides a snapshot of the exposure at the sampling time. Ideally, information on the evolution over time of the substances (or between sampling times) in the biological matrices is needed to refine the risk assessment.

Combined to HBM data based on exposure scenarios and exposure data, toxicokinetic (TK) modelling can link external to internal exposure (forward dosimetry) or internal to external exposure (reverse dosimetry) over time. A class of TK models, the Physiologically Based Kinetic (PBK) models, also called PBTK or PBPK, were identified as essential tools in risk assessment, and continuously gaining ground in regulatory applications. They describe in quantitative terms the Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion (ADME) processes of substances in the human body and subdivides the body in compartments representing organs connected by blood (Bois & Brochot, 2016). PBK models are able to derive on the effective, bioavailable concentration at the expected target site in order to better characterise the relationship between the exposure and the adverse effects (Andersen, 1995; Verner *et al.*, 2010).

Considering the continuously growing interest of using PBK models in the risk assessment (RA) process, guidelines for proper species, doses, and exposure scenarios extrapolations have been proposed (IPCS, 2010; OECD, 2021; U.S. EPA., 2006). The mechanistic basis of PBK models is well adapted to toxicological risk assessment, in particular for dealing with extrapolations inherent to these domains (*in vitro* to *in vivo*, laboratory animals to humans, various exposure or dosing schemes, etc.). In risk assessment, the use of PBK modelling in regulatory decision-making is still in discussion. The current guidelines (EMA, 2016; FDA, 2018) mainly focused on the information to provide in PBK model documentation regarding to pharmaceutical industry, which might further adapt the process of model development in regulatory applications (Verscheijden *et al.*, 2020). For example, experts in modelling in regulators to review of submitted models are limited, the applicability of PBK models to answer regulatory questions, the lack of transparency and accessibility, the easy use of these models by user-friendly platforms is limited, or the lack of *in vivo* data leading to

in vitro-to-*in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE) PBK models and raise the question of reliability of these models in risk assessment perspectives (Escher *et al.*, 2022). For the next step to help in a better acceptance of PBK models, three factors will need to be improved: dialogue and communication, training and guidance (Paini *et al.*, 2019).

The refinement and the development of PBK models for compounds in the PARC prioritisation process, with a large scientific and regulatory interest, is one of the final aims of this European partnership. Among other purposes, it is expected to fill the gaps in the assessment of the internal exposure (*i.e.* in the human body) of single compounds or mixtures. The previous European project, HBM4EU, has already identified and reviewed the available PBK models for about 30 compounds (Brochot *et al.*, 2019b; Sarigiannis *et al.*, 2017a), as well as the recent EFSA roadmap (Escher *et al.*, 2022). However, these reviews emphasised the lack or paucity of TK information for a high number of these prioritised compounds, particularly for the inhalation (very important for occupational settings) and dermal (very important for assessing exposure to cosmetics) exposure routes for which absorption and metabolism data are lacking for most substances. They also highlighted that models and data are lacking for sensitive populations such as pregnant women and fetuses, newborns, young children, or elderly.

In the PARC project on the refinement and development of PBK models for human risk assessment (project 6.2.2.a), PBK models will be refined or developed to address the different sensitivities resulting from the interindividual variability of population sub-groups by integrating the evolution of physiological and biochemical processes through life, the aggregation of multiple exposure routes and sources, the interpretation of biomonitoring data (*e.g.*, concentrations of parent compounds or metabolites in blood, urine, or other biological matrices), and the mixtures of substances. Different sources of data will be used (either from literature, or from synergies with work package (WP) 5), for refining or developing PBK models necessary for the use of internal dose metrics for risk assessment. While WP6 (this project in particular) will focus on the refinement of PBK models through lifetime, PBK modelling in WP5 will focus on the methodological data gaps in IVIVE PBK models with regard to (i) quantification of metabolites in liver/human metabolome, (ii) integration of active transport, and (iii) tiered testing strategies. The practical use of PBK models will be supported by increasing their availability in computational platforms for risk assessment as part of the PARC integrative model network (in close collaboration with the task 8.3). In summary, this project will be done in close collaboration with WP5 (generation of toxicokinetic data and IVIVE PBK models), WP4 (HBM data), WP8 (implementation in platforms), and WP2 (prioritisation of substances and exposure scenarios) and other activities of WP6 (*e.g.*, activity 6.2.1 on the aggregate exposures or activity 6.2.3 on mixtures).

As a first step of this PARC project, the aim of this report is to provide an inventory of PBK models currently available to assessing internal exposure during the life course in considering age dependent variation in organ physiology, metabolism and clearance from *in utero* to end of life. This will allow to provide some recommendations to fill the identified gaps and perspectives on the use of PBK models in risk assessment.

This deliverable provides an inventory of the human PBK models available published or developed by partners since the review done in the HBM4EU project in 2017 (Sarigiannis *et al.*, 2017a) and 2019 (Brochot *et al.*, 2019b) for the prioritised compounds, *i.e.* bisphenols, arsenic, lead, mercury, hexavalent chromium, mycotoxins, perfluorinated compounds and several pesticides (*e.g.*, pyrethroids, organophosphates). This search focused on different age groups or specific populations. This inventory allows us to identify the gaps, both in terms of models and parameters, and to inform other PARC WP and risk assessors. The report is organised as follows: the recent models identified for the prioritised substances are presented. Then the dynamic evolution of toxicokinetic processes and associated parameters (*e.g.*, the ontogeny of enzyme activities, transporters) are introduced. In a third section, the gaps are identified to then provide recommendations and perspectives. The appendices contain the detailed description of the PBK models as well as the global inventory PBK models' file.

2. Human PBK models for prioritised compounds

The compounds that will be dealt with priority in the PARC project were selected in consortium with mainly policy makers and regulators in substances/food safety and occupational health in European Union Member States, European institutions responsible for policy makers and agencies responsible for implementing EU regulations. The PARC strategy prioritised chemical families in considering pre-existing knowledge on exposure, hazardous properties including epidemiological data for some of the compounds and concerns on cumulative risks. The identification of the first set of priorities for PARC started before the launch of the Partnership with the legacy from HBM4EU and with a survey sent to the interim governing board members. In order to have a clearer view on the prioritisation strategy within the different WPs, a survey dedicated to the prioritisation of compounds and meetings with WP leaders and task leaders. The approach and results are overviewed in PARC deliverable D2.1 Prioritisation criteria report WP2. This process led to a prioritised list of 10 chemical families by PARC stakeholders (academia, HBM4EU workshop, European Commission, Ministries of several Member States). The PARC T6.2 task leaders on integrative risk assessment refined these prioritised chemicals groups with the EFSA and the European Commission to ensure synergies with results reported in EFSA opinions or ongoing discussions within working groups of DG SANTE. From all these discussions, per- and polyfluoroalkyls substances (PFAS), heavy metals, pesticides, and mycotoxins were prioritised in T6.2. In this project, we also added the bisphenols in the list of the compounds of interest as this family is still a great concern for health risk assessment for the European population (Meslin *et al.*, 2022).

The review was based on keyword research in commonly used scientific libraries (*e.g.*, Web of science, PubMed). The keywords used referred to the classes of compounds of interest. Furthermore, generic PBK models were included in the search criteria as they can simulate a wide range of compounds during different life stages. It is assumed that the different stages of life considered in this report (if it is not detailed in the text) are as follows: infants (from birth to 1 year), toddlers (from 1 to 3 years), children (from 3 to 10 years), teenagers (from 10 to 18 years), adults (from 18 to 65 years), and the elderly (from 65 years). The studies that referred only to animal species and not to humans were excluded. Different combinations of keywords were used, including several key words, such as 'Physiologically based pharmacokinetic (or toxicokinetic or biokinetic) model + PBPK (or PBK or PBTk or PBBK) + compound name + compound short name + human'.

The PBK models inventory file and the detailed information of each model (PBK models roadmaps including model description, parameter evaluation and model analysis) are available in Appendices (Annex 1 and Annex 2). For each class of compound, a summary is provided in the following subsections, with at the end of each subsection, a table that indicates the publication associated to the PBK model, the exact compound(s) considered, the exposure route(s), the biological matrix for which the model is able to run (*e.g.*, blood, urine),

and the targeted population. This key information was retained as suggested in the results of the HBM4EU project (Brochot *et al.*, 2019b; Sarigiannis *et al.*, 2017a).

2.1. Bisphenols

2.1.1. Presentation

The bisphenols (BPs) are a group of chemical compounds with two hydroxyphenyl functionalities. Bisphenol A (BPA) is the most common compound of this group, as it was used since 1930, widely extended in food packaging allowing BPA migration from food contact material to food, exposing the body via diet. BPA has been listed as an endocrine disruptor by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), as well as lately by ECHA (2018). Due to the regulation, the use of BPA analogues with similar chemical structures and behaviour has increased these last decades. The most common BPA analogues used today are bisphenol S (BPS), bisphenol F (BPF), bisphenol E (BPE), bisphenol AF (BPAF), bisphenol P (BPP) and bisphenol B (BPB). Some studies have demonstrated that BPA analogues show endocrine disrupting activities as observed for BPA and are present in foodstuffs (Gálvez-Ontiveros *et al.*, 2021). The primary source of exposure to BPs is through the diet, while dermal contact and inhalation are to a lesser extent other possible sources of exposure.

2.1.2. Description of the PBK models

In the HBM4EU project (Brochot *et al.*, 2019b; Sarigiannis *et al.*, 2017a), several models were reviewed for bisphenols: Edginton and Ritter (2009); Mielke and Gundert-Remy (2009); Sarigiannis *et al.* (2016); Sharma *et al.* (2018); Shin *et al.* (2004); Yang *et al.* (2015). Since this review, five new PBK models were identified, briefly presented below and summarized in the Table 1.

Karrer et al. (2018) aimed to compare the TK behaviours of BPA, BPS, BPF, and BPAF for different age groups after environmentally relevant external exposures by considering substance-specific metabolism kinetics and partitioning behaviour. This model account for 8 to 10 compartments and considers oral and dermal exposures. The model code is available and developed in R (version 3.3.2).

Gingrich et al. (2021) aimed to develop pregnancy-specific PBK models for BPA and BPS, using a common p-PBK model structure including 9 compartments for the mother and three for the fetuses. Oral exposure was considered and a global sensitivity analysis was performed. The model is available on the GitHub platform and was developed in Python, associated to the package 'Tellurium' (version 2.1.5).

Deepika et al. (2022) developed a sex specific PBK model for paediatric and adult populations with 8 compartments. Model is coded in GNU MCSim (version 6.2.0) with R and code is available upon request through GitHub. Oral exposure is considered with both BPA-G and BPA-

S metabolites through UGT and SULT (phase II) metabolism. Local sensitivity analysis was performed using the ‘FME’ package in R.

Hu et al. (2023) developed a dermal PBK for BPA, BPS, BPF and BPAF using controlled four volunteer human data. The model was adapted from Karrer *et al.* (2018) but some parameters were modified to fit the data. This model consists of 12 compartments with stomach, gut, liver, brain, fat, gonads, rich and slow, unexposed skin, exposed skin with skin surface depot, stratum corneum, viable epidermis and follicle. Uncertainty using Monte Carlo simulations was considered and a local sensitivity analysis was performed.

Wisniowska et al. (2023) aimed to implement dermal absorption in a conceptually different way as they intended to model the absorption of BPA from thermal paper through hand skin layers in PBK models, with a refined approach which involves a robust mechanistically description of skin anatomy and physiology. The model was developed with the Simcyp simulator (version 21), where the associated code is not publicly available but available on request. No information was provided on the PBK model used for oral exposure and the associated compartments considered in the model. However, a more detailed description of the ADME process for dermal exposure has been provided and may be further implemented in future PBK models that consider dermal exposure. The targeted population is adults, and both blood and cumulative urinary excretion profiles were provided for BPA and metabolites.

Table 1. Summary of recently published PBK models for bisphenols.

References	Compounds	Exposure routes	Biological matrix	Population
Karrer <i>et al.</i> (2018)	BPA, BPS, BPF, BPAF	Oral and dermal	Blood, urine	Infants (6days–3 months), toddlers (1-3 years), children (3-10 years), teenagers (10-18 years), adult women and men (18-45 years)
Gingrich <i>et al.</i> (2021)	BPA, BPS	Oral	Blood	Pregnancy
Deepika <i>et al.</i> (2022)	BPA	Oral	Blood, urine	Adult, paediatric (6-11 years)
Hu <i>et al.</i> (2023)	BPA, BPS, BPF, BPAF	Dermal	Blood, urine	Adult
Wiśniowska <i>et al.</i> (2023)	BPA	Dermal and Oral	Blood, urine	Adult

2.2. Metals

2.2.1. Presentation

Metals are naturally occurring elements that have a wide range of everyday uses, including industrial, medical, and technological applications. Some common examples of metals include arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), mercury (Hg), lead (Pb) and chromium (Cr). Although metals are essential for many biological processes, they can also be toxic in high doses and cause a range of adverse health effects. Several PBK models were specifically developed for metals and some were used in risk assessment on health, especially applied to workers (Chalvatzaki *et al.*, 2013; Hack *et al.*, 2007; Teeguarden *et al.*, 2007).

2.2.2. Description of the PBK models

2.2.2.1. Arsenic

Since the model inventory development in HBM4EU project was completed, there are no recent models for arsenic. In brief, the available models are presented below and can be easily accessed from here:

El-Masri and Kenyon (2008) developed a PBK model for iAs (inorganic arsenic) and its methylated metabolites. Included compounds were iAs, As(III), As(V), MMA(V), DMA(V). This PBK model was developed for adults and the exposure routes that were considered during the implementation of the model were the inhalation and ingestion paths. Dermal exposure was supposed to be insignificant. El-Masri and Kenyon provided all the available parameters and the differential equations used in the annex of their publication.

Yu (1999a, 1999b) implemented two PBK/TK models, one for children (a) and one for adults (b). The metabolites of iAs that were considered as significant were the same as the ones of El – Masri's. Exposure routes were considered only through ingestion. The other routes of exposure were assumed as insignificant. Seven perfused tissue compartments were taken into account during the implementation of the model.

Mann *et al.* (1996a, 1996b) developed a model (b) which was an extension of an existed PBK model for hamsters and rabbits (a). The model considered only the ingestion and inhalation exposure routes during the implementation and consisted of 6 tissue compartments. ADME procedures were carried out for iAs and the rest of its metabolites (As(III), MMA(V), DMA(V)).

2.2.2.2. Cadmium

Pouillot *et al.* (2022) aimed to predict the internal kinetics of cadmium especially in the kidney burden and the urinary concentration for the U.S. population. The model follows the structure of Kjellström and Nordberg model (Kjellström & Nordberg, 1978), with a model of 8 compartments (lung, intestine, 3 blood compartments: plasma, erythrocytes and metallothionein, liver, kidney and other tissues), two routes of excretion (urine and feces) and 21 kinetic parameters (detailed in model roadmap). Some parameters were modified

considering previous models. The parameters C5 (fraction of gut intestine –tract Cd retained in epithelium) is gendered as in Béchaux *et al.* (2014). Fransson *et al.* (2014) derived the parameters C7, C8, C16, C17, C19 and C20 (fraction of uptake pool transferred to whole blood, maximum mass of Cd in uptake pool, rate of transfer of Cd in erythrocytes to metallothionein, rate of transfer of Cd in metallothionein to kidney, age-specific rate constant for transfer of Cd in kidney to urine and fraction of Cd in plasma and erythrocytes that contribute to cadmium whole blood) by robust inferences on the Kjellström and Nordberg model parameters matched with human kidney cortex, blood and urinary Cd measurements. Moreover, the estimations of body weights and creatinine excretions were adapted for the U.S. population, with regards to age, gender and race (CDC, 2021). A stochastic model was developed to integrate an inter-individual variability with a Pert distribution (Vose, 2006) on several parameters (C5, C7, C16, C17, C19 and C20). Biomonitoring data from smokers and individuals exposed to Cd in the workplace are excluded from the exposure model, which focuses on dietary exposures. The model's evaluation focused on urinary cadmium concentration adjusted for creatinine excretion, and the estimated kidney burdens could not be validated due to a lack of data for a representative population. Nonetheless, the 1:60 ratio for Urinary-Cd:Kidney-Cd was used to accept the model (Akerstrom *et al.*, 2013; Fransson *et al.*, 2014). The code of the deterministic model (Kjellström and Nordberg model) is available under R in the supplementary materials and the package ‘deSolve’ was used to solve the differential equations (Soetaert *et al.*, 2010). The PBTK model was implemented in an open access web-based tool (https://fda-riskmodels.foodrisk.org/Cadmium_FDA_PBPk/).

2.2.2.3. Chromium

Chromium can exist in several oxidation states, most often found in the trivalent (+3) and hexavalent (+6) oxidation states (Towill *et al.*, 1978). High concentrations of hexavalent chromium can be measured in the environment, mainly due to industrial emissions (Kotaš & Stasicka, 2000), but can also be found in house dust (Stern, 2010) and in food (Mandiwana *et al.*, 2011). Oral exposure (children in contact with toys) and dermal contact (cosmetics and leather articles) have been identified as the main exposure routes for adults and children. Human exposures to chromium can cause health effects, as airway irritation, obstruction, asthma and cancer (Langård, 1990; O'Flaherty, 1995).

Among the three available chromium PBK models in literature for human, two of them (Kirman *et al.*, 2013; O'Flaherty *et al.*, 2001) were already detailed in the HBM4EU deliverable (Sarigiannis *et al.*, 2017a). The model from Kirman *et al.* (2013) was updated in 2017 but not reviewed in the HBM4EU project. The three models were coded in ACSL. Table 2 summarized the human PBK models available for chromium.

Kirman *et al.* (2017) aimed to update a previously developed PBK model for Cr(VI) in mice, rats, and humans (Kirman *et al.*, 2013; Kirman *et al.*, 2012). This model aims to reflect an improved understanding of the TK of the gastrointestinal tract following oral exposures. Three improvements were made on: (1) the reduction model from Cr(VI) reduced to Cr(III) in the

gastrointestinal tract, (2) a more realistic depiction of rodent drinking water exposure patterns, (3) parameterization of the model to identify human populations that may be particularly sensitive to Cr(VI) exposure. A model structure similar to that of Kirman *et al.* (2013) was adopted, *i.e.* via oral ingestion exposure, and 9 compartments were considered: gastrointestinal lumen, oral mucosa, stomach, small intestinal tissue, blood, liver, kidney, bone and a combined compartment for remaining tissues. The model accounts for lifetime physiological processes, *i.e.* neonate (0-3 months), child (3 months-6 y.o), youth (6-18y.o), adult (18-60 y.o), elderly (60-75 y.o), where age-specific values for body weight, tissue and lumen volumes, and transit rates were obtained from published reviews for these age groups. The model is coded in ACSLX (AegisTG, version 3.0) and available in the supplementary material of the article.

Table 2. Summary of available PBK models for chromium.

References	Compounds	Exposure routes	Biological matrix	Population
O'Flaherty <i>et al.</i> (2001)	CrVI, CrIII	Oral	Blood, urine	Adult
Kirman <i>et al.</i> (2013)	CrVI, CrIII	Oral	Blood	Adult
Kirman <i>et al.</i> (2017)	CrVI, CrIII	Oral	Gastric concentrations and pyloric Flux	Neonate, child, teen, adult

2.2.2.4. Lead

Humans are exposed to lead through dust inhalation and ingestion via soil or animals and plants products from contaminated soil, as well via drinking water due to the corrosion of older fixtures or from the solder that connects pipes (Dudka & Miller, 1999; Hawley, 1985; Rabinowitz *et al.*, 1985). No new PBK models were developed since the HBM4EU review (Brochot *et al.*, 2019b).

However, it seems important to point out that the study of **Tebby *et al.* (2022)** provided a rewritten O'Flaherty model (initially coded in ACSL) in R (version 3.6.1) and also implemented in GNU MCSim (version 6.2.0). Some substance-specific parameters were updated according to other works. Additionally, **Sweeney (2021)** applied the O'Flaherty model to workers in adding some refinements on parameters. Table 3 presents the summary of the main PBK models available for lead.

Table 3. Summary of the main available human PBK models for lead.

References	Compounds	Exposure routes	Biological matrix	Population
Oflaherty (1993)	Pb	Oral and inhalation	Blood	Adults
Oflaherty (1995)	Pb	Oral and inhalation	Blood	Children
Sharma and Reddy (2012)	Pb	Oral	Blood and urine	Adults
Sweeney (2021)	Pb	Oral and inhalation	Blood	Workers
Tebby <i>et al.</i> (2022) (from O’Flaherty model)	Pb	Oral and inhalation	Blood	Adults and children

2.2.2.5. Mercury

Since the conduction of HBM4EU deliverable (Brochot *et al.*, 2019b), no other PBK models for Hg have been implemented. The work carried out in the framework of HBM4EU project is briefly presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Summary of available mercury PBK models. Adapted from here.

References	Compounds	Exposure Routes	Biological matrix	Populations
Gearhart <i>et al.</i> (1995)	MeHg	Gestational	Urine	Adults and fetuses
Ou <i>et al.</i> (2018)	MeHg	Oral	Urine	Adults, infants, pregnant and breastfeeding women
Clewell <i>et al.</i> (1999)	MeHg	Oral	Urine	Adults and infants
Carrier <i>et al.</i> (2001)	MeHg, iHg	Oral	Urine	Adults

2.3. Mycotoxins

2.3.1. Presentation

Mycotoxins are toxic secondary metabolites produced by filamentous fungi (*e.g.*, *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, *Alternaria* and *Penicillium*) that occur naturally on food crops infecting feed and food (Abrunhosa *et al.*, 2016). They can contaminate food crops pre-harvest – during growth of the crop plant or post-harvest when crops are processed, packaged, distributed or (improperly) stored. Conditions such as long-term storage under higher temperatures and humidity provide a wealthy environment for fungi to grow (Alshannaq & Yu, 2017). Food and agriculture organisation (FAO) of the United Nations estimated that approximately 25% of cereals produced in the world are contaminated with at least one mycotoxin (Rice & Ross, 1994). Due to their harmful effects (including carcinogenic, estrogenic, teratogenic, hepatotoxic, mutagenic, nephrotoxic, neurotoxic, respiratory and immunosuppressive effects (Hamad *et al.*, 2023), mycotoxins pose an important global risk to public health via oral exposure. Most mycotoxins are chemically and thermally stable during food processing (including cooking, boiling, baking, frying, roasting, and pasteurization) and can also reach the human plate via animal products such as meat, eggs, milk as a result of the animal eating contaminated feed (Alshannaq & Yu, 2017). In addition to oral exposure, inhalation and absorption are considered as well regarding mycotoxin human exposure, especially in the case of occupational exposure (Viegas *et al.*, 2019). While there are over 300 known mycotoxins, the most relevant compounds regarding food safety are zearalenone (ZEN), aflatoxin B1 (AFB1), deoxynivalenol (DON), ochratoxin A (OTA), fumonisins (FBs) patulin (PAT), ergot alkaloids, *Alternaria*, enniatins and trichothecenes (Abrunhosa *et al.*, 2016).

2.3.2. Description of the PBK models

The search identified three specific human PBK models for ZEN and one for AFB1. A specific human model for DON was available at the RIVM (Notenboom *et al.*, 2023). For other mycotoxins, *i.e.* nivalenol, fumonisins, T-2/HT-2, ochratoxin A, *alternaria* toxins and enniatins, no specific PBK models were found. The HBM4EU additional deliverables (Brochot *et al.*, 2019b; Sarigiannis *et al.*, 2017a) did not list additional PBK models of interest.

Zearalenone (ZEN)

Shin *et al.* (2009) published the first human PBK model for ZEN for oral and intravenous (IV) exposure. The model describes an adult and includes 14 compartments (*i.e.* venous blood, arterial blood, lung, kidney, heart, testis, brain, muscle, adipose tissue, spleen, stomach, small intestine and liver). Additional lumen and conjugated compartments should not be considered as compartments. While the model only included the parent compound, it did include glucuronidation, biliary excretion, enterohepatic recirculation and fast (immediate) and slow (delayed) absorption processes. The human model was made by upscaling from the rat PBK model using allometric scaling according to body weight. The model is not able to provide concentration-time profiles for urine or feces. The model was not verified against human data. The rat model was validated against rat data; however, it is unclear whether the same data was used for parameter fitting. Since the human model is based on rat-based substance-specific parameters and partition coefficients, it is possible that the model does not predict well for humans. No sensitivity analysis, nor uncertainty analysis were performed. The model code was written in Berkeley Madonna and is not provided in the article.

Mukherjee *et al.* (2014) further developed the model of Shin *et al.* (2009). The adult human PBK model for the oral exposure of ZEN includes the primary metabolites to simulate critical metabolic pathways in the gastrointestinal and hepatic systems. The model describes the metabolization of ZEN into zearanol (α and β), zearalenol (α and β), zearalenone and their glucuronidated conjugates. Compared to the model of Shin *et al.* (2009), excretion via the kidney and metabolism from the gut were added. The model contains thirteen compartments (*i.e.* lung, heart, brain, muscle, fat, gonads, spleen, stomach, kidney, venous and arterial blood). The additional lumen compartment should not be considered as a compartment. The way various parameters were obtained is not well described and most parameters are rat based. The model was validated against data for total radioactivity which was most likely also used for parameter optimization. While the model predictions of total ZEN agreed well with the data for venous blood and feces, predictions for total ZEN in urine do not look as good. Additionally, simulations of the metabolites were not checked against human data. The model code was written in MATLAB Release 2013a and some equations can be found in the article.

Mendez-Catala *et al.* (2021) developed a human PBK model which included microbial and hepatic metabolism of ZEN following oral and IV in order to predict systematic concentrations of ZEN and to obtain insight into the contribution of metabolism by the intestinal microbiota to the overall metabolism of ZEN. Next to ZEN, concentration-time profiles could only be obtained for the bioactive metabolite α -zearalenol (α -ZEL). Other metabolites (*i.e.* β -zearalenol, and the glucuronidated conjugates of ZEN and α -ZEL) were included solely to describe metabolic conversion. The model for ZEN contains seven compartments (*i.e.* blood, fat, rapidly perfused tissue [heart, lung, brain], slowly perfused tissue [skin, muscle, bone], liver and intestine). The intestinal compartment consisted of three separate compartments including the small intestinal lumen, small intestinal tissue, and large intestinal lumen. The

small intestinal lumen was divided into seven sub-compartments. The additional stomach compartment should not be considered as a compartment. The model for α -ZEN contains only five compartments (*i.e.* blood, fat, rapidly perfused tissue, slowly perfused tissue and liver). Metabolism and absorption parameters were obtained from *in vitro* studies. The model predictions of the human model were not evaluated over time. The cumulative urinary concentrations of total ZEN (ZEN and ZEN-glucuronide) reported by two studies at oral doses of 1.43 mg/kg bw and 0.2 μ g/gk bw were, respectively, 2-fold underestimated, and 2-fold overestimated. All parameters related to the glucuronidation of ZEN and α -ZEN were seen in the sensitivity analysis as influential. The model code was written in Berkeley Madonna and is provided in the supplementary material.

Deoxynivalenol (DON)

Notenboom *et al.* (2023) describes a human adult PBK model for DON and its metabolites DON-3-glucuronide (DON-3-GlcA) and DON-15-glucuronide (DON-15-GlcA) following oral exposure. The model structure is based on the generic IndusChemFate model, however several compartments are lumped together as richly perfused and slowly perfused compartments. In total, 9 compartments are included (*i.e.* lung, adipose tissue, stomach + intestine, liver, kidney, venous blood, arterial blood and richly [brain, bone marrow] and slowly [bone, muscle, skin] perfused organs). The model is able to simulate urinary concentrations over time and cumulative urinary excretion. The oral absorption rate constant and excretion fractions are fitted based on urinary excretion data from Mengelers *et al.* (2019). Due to the type of data used for metabolism parameters, the model is only applicable for oral doses around 1 μ g/kg bw. The model simulations were evaluated using the simulations of the biokinetic model described in Mengelers *et al.* (2019) which was fitted on HBM data (same data as used for fitting the two parameters). No sensitivity or uncertainty analysis were performed.

Aflatoxin B1 (AFB1)

Gilbert-Sandoval *et al.* (2020) published a human (and rat) PBK-model based on *in vitro* and *in silico* input for aflatoxin B1 (AFB1) to predict its acute liver toxicity. The model program used was Berkeley Madonna version 8.3.18, where tissue and blood flow fractions were obtained from Brown *et al.* (1997) and tissue:blood partition coefficients were calculated based on the approach of DeJongh *et al.* (1997) (using LogP of AFB1). Compartments described were blood, liver, fat, kidney, richly perfused tissues and slowly perfused tissues, and were considered to be well-stirred compartments. Also, a seven-compartment intestinal model was used for oral absorption of AFB1 (similar to the one described for the ZEN model by Mendez-Catala *et al.* (2021)). The uptake rate included was previously reported by Jubert *et al.* (2009). The *in vitro* Michaelis-Menten input parameters (V_{max} and K_m) of the two most abundant metabolites AFQ1 and AFBO were included in the model, based on literature reported data (Kamdem *et al.*, 2006). The metabolites were included for the clearance of AFB1, not to model their blood or tissue concentrations. The blood concentration of AFB1 was predicted at a dose of

0.374 ng/kg bw and evaluated against *in vivo* data reported in four individuals (Jubert *et al.*, 2009), where the model slightly underpredicted the peak blood concentrations.

Table 5. Summary of PBK models available for mycotoxins.

References	Compounds	Exposure routes	Biological matrix	Population
Shin <i>et al.</i> (2009)	ZEN	Oral + IV	Blood	Adult
Mukherjee <i>et al.</i> (2014)	ZEN + metabolites	Oral	Blood, urine, feces	Adult (also used for children)
Mendez-Catala <i>et al.</i> (2021)	ZEN + metabolites	Oral + IV	Blood, urine	Adult
Notenboom <i>et al.</i> (2023)	DON + metabolites	Oral	Blood, urine	Adult*
Gilbert-Sandoval <i>et al.</i> (2020)	AFB1	Oral	Blood	Adult

* All IndusChemFate populations possible on request to authors

2.4. Perfluorinated compounds

2.4.1. Presentation

Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are a family of persistent compounds containing thousands of synthetic chemicals and composed of carbon, fluorine and other elements. PFAS are known to accumulate in environment, wildlife and some PFAS are very slowly excreted from humans due to their long half-lives. The major source of PFAS exposure is dietary intake including drinking water as well as a minor contribution from dust ingestion and inhalation (Domingo *et al.*, 2012; Rovira *et al.*, 2019). Only a few PFAS are relative well studied in experimental and epidemiology studies illustrating a negative effect on human health (De Silva *et al.*, 2021). PFAS are supposed to cause immunosuppression, and reproductive toxicity, and cancer and affect the human endocrinal system, among other effects ([Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances \(PFASs\) - ECHA \(europa.eu\)](https://www.echa.europa.eu/per-and-polyfluoroalkyl-substances-pfas)). There are many PFASs (*e.g.*, C2 to C18 perfluorocarboxylic acids and perfluorosulfonic acids, various fluorotelomers and alternatives to the already restricted PFOA and PFOS such as GenX and DONA) which are studied extensively by researchers around the world.

HBM4EU report on deliverable 12.1 (Sarigiannis *et al.*, 2017a) has mentioned multicompartmental models for PFOS and PFOA. Nine compartments perfusion-limited PBK model for PFOS and PFOA was reported in monkey and human with no metabolism (Loccisano *et al.*, 2011). This model was validated in monkey and scaled to human to simulate the data collected from residents of two communities exposed to PFOA in drinking water. Another model from Loccisano *et al.* (2013) was an extension of rat (Loccisano *et al.*, 2012) to gestational and lactation PBK with addition of mammary tissue, placental, fetal and milk compartment. Fàbrega *et al.* (2014) developed another model for PFOS and PFOA based on the Loccisano model explaining the kinetic of resorption by renal transporter in filtrate compartment and resorption through a saturable process. In 2016, another model was developed (Fàbrega *et al.*, 2016) where uncertainty was included in the biochemical parameters to improve the PBK model predictions. In both these models, the simulated results were validated with the human autopsy data including measured PFAS concentrations in plasma and other organs (Pérez *et al.*, 2013).

2.4.2. Description of the PBK models

Recent PBK models available for the four PFAS (PFOS, PFOA, PFNA and PFHxS) in the literature were searched and documented, as also detailed in the recent review performed by East *et al.* (2023). A summary is provided for the six models in Table 6.

Several studies have been using PBK models that were originally developed based on rat data to perform human health risk assessment for PFOA (Worley *et al.*, 2017), PFOS (Kamiya *et al.*, 2020), PFNA (Kim *et al.*, 2019) and PFHxS (Kim *et al.*, 2018) by extrapolating the rat PBK model to the human situation. The PBK model from Worley *et al.* (2017) incorporated a detailed renal excretion module to describe the active transport and resorption of PFOA, which was fitted to

human data. The PBK model from Kamiya *et al.* (2020) was a relatively simple model comprising only gut, liver, kidney and the rest of the body compartment and human kinetic parameters were either predicted based on allometric scaling or fitted to human data. In the studies performed by Kim *et al.* (2018, 2019), gender differences in the kinetics of the PFAS was predicted based on allometric scaling of the kinetic parameters for the rat data. Unfortunately, the predictions for PFNA and PFHxS could not be compared to human data due to the lack of epidemiological data.

Wu *et al.* (2015) developed a model for PFOA and PFOS from fetal exposure to young adult age to describe the physiological changes of the female population aged 0-20 years to assess the epidemiologic association between PFAS and delayed menarche. Later, **Ruark *et al.* (2017)** adapted the model of Wu *et al.* (2015) to describe the physiological changes during menopause in order to assess the epidemiological association between PFAS exposure and the altered timing of menopause. Several other PBK models have been developed recently to describe the physiological changes during pregnancy and lactation and the transfer of PFAS from mothers to the fetuses and child.

Brochot *et al.* (2019a) developed PFOS and PFOA pregnancy and lactational PBK model adapted from lifetime model to evaluate the fetal exposure for the Spanish INMA birth cohort. The PBK model was used for reverse dosimetry to calculate the time-varying daily intake of mothers. A generic PBK model was adapted which was evaluated with human biomonitoring data. GNU MCSim (version 6.2.0) was used for the PBK with Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) simulations to calibrate the model in a Bayesian framework. Fetal exposure was simulated in target organs over the pregnancy to improve the characterization of prenatal exposure during susceptibility window.

A PFOS PBK model by **Chou and Lin (2019)** was developed with the objective to evaluate species-specific (mice, rat, monkeys and human) toxicokinetic parameters and calculate human equivalent dose (HED) by considering point of departure (PoD) from toxicity study in rat and monkeys for PFOS. The model consists of five compartments (gut, liver, small intestine, kidney, stomach and rest of body) with oral and IV as route of exposure. The model was calibrated using MCMC simulation and local sensitivity analysis was performed. Independent datasets were used for evaluation of the model for plasma, liver and kidney. The model was coded in R and code is freely available.

A PFOS PBK model by **Deepika *et al.* (2021)** was developed for human life stages (0 to 90 years) with oral route as the exposure to predict the risk in sensitive population. It consists of 9 compartments (gut, liver, brain, kidney, lung, fat, bone marrow, skin and rest of body) for humans with resorption from kidney transporter. The model was validated with human data from different organs obtained by autopsy (Pérez *et al.*, 2013). Parameters like the unbound fraction was scaled based on age considering variation in albumin levels. Global sensitivity

analysis was conducted using the 'pksensi' R-package. The model is coded in GNU MCSim with R and code is available on GitHub upon request.

Another model including gestational and lactational stages for rat and human was developed by **Chou and Lin (2021)** with 8 compartments (liver, fat, mammary tissue, kidney, rest of body, amniotic fluid, fetal liver and fetal rest of body). Oral route was the major exposure route with no metabolism. In addition, kidney transporters were included in the model. PBK model was validated using rat and human biomonitoring data, and goodness-of-fit was calculated with predicted to observed ratio of 2. Local sensitivity analysis has been performed for both rat and human based on area under the curve (AUC) for concentration of PFOS in maternal, fetal and neonatal plasma for rats and human during gestation and lactation. Model is coded in R with the 'mrgsolve' and 'FME' packages and code is available on GitHub.

A PFOA model by **Husøy *et al.* (2023)** was developed for adults based on the model from **Loccisano *et al.* (2011)** and **EFSA (2020)**. The PBK model comprises 9 compartments: plasma, gut, liver, fat, skin, kidney, filtrate compartment of urine, storage compartment of urine, and a compartment for the rest of the body. The original model was modified with inclusion of dermal absorption, faecal excretion and some changes in the urinary compartments. As PFOA has been found to be present in many cosmetics items and the dermal absorption was found to be significantly higher than previously reported (**Abraham & Monien, 2022**), the model was further extended with dermal exposure to PFOA from PCPs. The model is coded in R and the R 'pksensi' package was used to evaluate the uncertainty and global sensitivity of the PFOA model (**Hsieh *et al.*, 2020**). Validation of the model was performed using the data from **Emmett *et al.* (2006)** and individual data from the EuroMix biomonitoring study (**Husøy *et al.*, 2019**). The R code is in open access on GitHub.

A PFHxS PBK model by **Sweeney (2022)** consider sex-specific differences covering human lifetime with five compartments (kidney, liver, gut, adipose, and rest tissue). Menstrual loss from plasma has also been included. This model is refined from **Fàbrega *et al.* (2015)** and **Ruark *et al.* (2017)** for physiological and biochemical parameters. Total intake is considered directly to plasma and model was validated using NHANES data based on age and location. Local sensitivity analysis was performed and model was coded using ACSLX and is available.

Table 6. Summary of published PFAS PBK models.

References	Compounds	Exposure routes	Biological matrix	Population
Loccisano <i>et al.</i> (2011)	PFOS, PFOA	Oral, IV	Blood, urine	Adult
Loccisano <i>et al.</i> (2013)	PFOS, PFOA	Oral, IV	Blood, urine	Pregnancy, Lactational and gestational
Fàbrega <i>et al.</i> (2014)	PFOS, PFOA	Oral	Blood, urine	Human
Fàbrega <i>et al.</i> (2015)	PFBS, PFHxS, PFOS, PFDS, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFTeDA	Oral	Blood, urine	Human
Fàbrega <i>et al.</i> (2016)	PFOS, PFOA	Oral	Blood, urine	Human
Brochot <i>et al.</i> (2019a)	PFOS, PFOA	Oral	Blood	Pregnancy Human
Rovira <i>et al.</i> (2019)	PFOS, PFOA	Oral, Dermal, Inhalation	Blood, urine	Pregnancy Human
Chou and Lin (2019)	PFOS	Oral, IV	Blood, urine	Adult Human
Deepika <i>et al.</i> (2021)	PFOS	Oral	Blood, urine	Human life stage (0-90 years)
Chou and Lin (2021)	PFOS	Oral	Blood, urine	Gestational, Lactational, Pregnancy
Sweeney (2022)	PFHxS	Total Intake	Blood, urine	Human life stage
Husøy <i>et al.</i> (2023)	PFOA	Oral and dermal	Blood, urine	Adult human

2.5. Pesticides

2.5.1. Presentation

Pesticides are a broad group of various chemical families that are applied as herbicides, insecticides, nematocides, molluscicides and fungicides, among others, to prevent, destroy or control any pest. Humans are usually exposed to pesticides repeatedly consuming fruits and vegetables containing residuals of pesticides (Tudi *et al.*, 2022). However, dermal exposure with a high acute concentration might occur in an incident of occupational and/or accidental exposure (Tudi *et al.*, 2022). Important insecticides include organophosphates and pyrethroids, which affect the nervous system of insects but also non-targeted species such as human.

Organophosphates need often to be bioactivated via P450 metabolism pathways into the neurotoxic metabolite, which potentially inhibit cholinesterases such as acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase. In addition, chronic low dose exposure to organophosphates has been associated with noticeable changed neurobehavioral development and reduced intellectual development in children (Bouchard *et al.*, 2011; González-Alzaga *et al.*, 2014).

Human PBK models for the pesticide group organophosphates mainly exist for chlorpyrifos. In total, we identified 17 articles describing human PBK models for chlorpyrifos applied for risk assessment purposes. The first PBK model developed by Timchalk *et al.* (2002b) served as basis to estimate chlorpyrifos and its metabolite (chlorpyrifos-oxon and 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol) concentrations in children (Beamer *et al.*, 2012; Hinderliter *et al.*, 2011; Lu *et al.*, 2010; Wason *et al.*, 2012), adults (Foxenberg *et al.*, 2011; Zhao *et al.*, 2019; Zhao *et al.*, 2022) and workers (Bouchard *et al.*, 2005). Moreover, most of the PBK models only model oral exposure. Beamer *et al.* (2012), Poet *et al.* (2014) and Zurlinden and Reifeld (2018) modelled chlorpyrifos exposure via ingestion, inhalation and dermal contact. While Smith *et al.* (2014) developed a human life stage PBK model, they did not explicitly incorporate a pregnancy submodel in the modelling framework. Later, Poet *et al.* (2017) made some adaptations to the Smith *et al.* (2014) model to incorporate the changes in physiological parameters during pregnancy and used the model to estimate the human health risk from chlorpyrifos during pregnancy. Two out of 17 PBK models published in 2019 and onwards (Zhao *et al.*, 2019; Zhao *et al.*, 2022) focused on modelling inter-individual differences in biotransformation. The model of Zhao *et al.* (unpublished) includes very early pregnancy due to the incorporation of an uterus compartment without barrier.

For Azinphos-methyl, only a simpler toxicokinetic models exist (Carrier & Brunet, 1999).

Furthermore, a PBK model of the broad-spectrum N-methyl carbamate pesticide carbofuran was developed in the Exposure Related Dose Estimating Model (ERDEM) system, but only validated for rat data (Blancato *et al.*, 2006; Zhang *et al.*, 2007).

For triazophos, dichlorvos, omethoate, formetanate, carbofuran, primiphos-methyl and methomyl, no PBK model was found during the literature search.

Pyrethroids are insecticides widely used for domestic and professional uses (U.S. EPA., 2011). They are synthetic products derived from the natural substance which is permethrin. Pyrethroids are divided in two classes: type-I (with a cyano group) and type-II (without a cyano group). Toxicokinetic varies depending on the compounds as it is impacted by the chirality property, leading to several stereoisomers in the environment. Routes of exposure are mainly by food consumption (Darney *et al.*, 2018), but dermal contact and inhalation should not be underestimated (Hermant *et al.*, 2018; Tomalik-Scharte *et al.*, 2005). Pyrethroids are suspected to affect the neuronal and hormonal systems (Bradberry *et al.*, 2005; Gotoh *et al.*, 1998). Pyrethroids interact with voltage-dependent sodium channels, altering the function of neurons (Soderlund *et al.*, 2002). Metabolites are often detected in urine samples in human biomonitoring surveys, implying an exposure to parent compound(s). These metabolites can be specific to a parent compound or non-specific if they are common to several parent compounds which represent cumulative exposure to pyrethroids (Ueyama *et al.*, 2010). The literature search focused on the main common metabolites identified in HBM surveys, that come from pyrethroids parent compounds (*i.e.* permethrin (type I), deltamethrin (type II), cypermethrin (type II) and cyfluthrin (type II)).

Other pesticides are also of interest, as numerous substances exist in co-exposures and can affect human health, as it is the case for organophosphates or pyrethroids. Only three PBK models were found for three pesticides (haloxyfop, chlordecone, epiryfrenacil) since the HBM4EU review (Brochot *et al.*, 2019b).

2.5.2. Description of the PBK models

2.5.2.1. Organophosphates

The description of the first PBK model describing the toxicokinetic of chlorpyrifos is briefly reminded below.

Chlorpyrifos

Timchalk *et al.* (2002a); Timchalk *et al.* (2002b) developed the first human PBK model for chlorpyrifos that were the bases for subsequent PBK models. The aim of these models was to integrate validated human tissue concentrations with cholinesterase inhibitions. Timchalk *et al.* (2002b) established a PBK model for chlorpyrifos including nine compartments (*i.e.* skin, fat, brain, liver, diaphragm, a two-compartment gastrointestinal tract, kidney, a rapid perfused compartment and a slowly perfused compartment). Chlorpyrifos was either absorbed via skin (dermal exposure) or the gastrointestinal tract (oral exposure). Chlorpyrifos has not been detected in human urine and elimination is assumed to only take place through biotransformation. In the liver, biotransformation of chlorpyrifos to the metabolites chlorpyrifos-oxon and 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPy) via CYP450 pathways was simulated

as a Michaelis-Menten kinetic. Chlorpyrifos-oxon and TCPy were eliminated by a first-order kinetic constant rate in the kidney. The simulated time-course of the TCPy concentrations in blood and urine agreed well to those measured in male volunteers exposed to 5 mg chlorpyrifos/kg dermally and 0.5 mg chlorpyrifos/kg orally as reported by Nolan *et al.* (1984). The distribution of chlorpyrifos-oxon, the bioactive metabolite inhibiting cholinesterases` in blood, liver, brain and diaphragm, was further simulated in a similar way as its parent compound excluding the skin compartment. Measured plasma cholinesterase inhibition in the same male subjects volunteered in Nolan *et al.* (1984) also agreed well with simulated inhibition time courses. Moreover, Timchalk *et al.* (2002a) investigated human chlorpyrifos-oxon polymorphism applying Monte Carlo analysis contributing to inter-individual variability on the theoretical concentration of chlorpyrifos-oxon in the human brain over a range of chlorpyrifos doses. The code was written in the ASCL software and model equations are provided in Timchalk *et al.* (2002b).

Since the HBM4EU review (Brochot *et al.*, 2019b), four new PBK models were published and described below (Table 7):

Table 7. Summary of recently published PBK models for organophosphates, including the first model developed for chlorpyrifos.

References	Compounds	Exposure routes	Biological matrix	Population
Timchalk <i>et al.</i> (2002a); Timchalk <i>et al.</i> (2002b)	Chlorpyrifos and metabolites	Dermal, Oral ingestion	Blood, Urine	Adults
Poet <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Chlorpyrifos and metabolites	Oral ingestion	Blood	Infants, pregnant women and adults
Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2019); Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Chlorpyrifos and metabolites	Oral ingestion	Blood, Urine	Adults
Zhao <i>et al.</i> unpublished	Chlorpyrifos and metabolites	Oral ingestion	Blood, Urine	Pregnant women
Carrier and Brunet (1999)	Azinphos-methyl and metabolite	Oral ingestion	Urine	Adults

The PBK model of **Poet et al. (2017)** aims to expand the life stage PBK model developed by Smith *et al.* (2014) to create a model of inhibition of red blood cell (RBC) acetylcholinesterase from oral exposures to CPF and CPF-oxon that reflects the impacts of interindividual variation in physiology and metabolism. In addition to the accounting for different life stages in Smith *et al.* (2014), this model includes the physiological and anatomical changes that occur during pregnancy. The model was developed under acslX (version 3.0.2.1) and is available on request. Interethnic differences in chlorpyrifos kinetics between Chinese and Caucasian populations were accounted for by **Zhao et al. (2019)**. Hereby, the PBK model from Timchalk *et al.* (2002b) was reduced to five compartments (*i.e.* fat, liver, gastrointestinal tract, a rapid perfused compartment, and a slowly perfused compartment). Biotransformation and excretion of the metabolites chlorpyrifos-oxon, TCPy, diethyl thiophosphate (DETP) and diethyl phosphate (DEP) were modelled in the liver. Zhao *et al.* (2019) incorporated interethnic differences in biotransformation of four different P450 pathways in the PBK model as scaled Michaelis-Menten kinetics gained from Chinese and Caucasian liver microsomes. Biotransformation of chlorpyrifos to chlorpyrifos-oxon is catalyzed dominantly by CYP2B6 and CYP3A4 and to TCPy and DETP by CYP2C19 and CYP3A4. The detoxification pathway of chlorpyrifos-oxon is catalyzed by the A-esterase paraoxonase (PON 1) leading to the metabolites TCPy and DEP. The simulations for identical exposures indicated that bioactivation of chlorpyrifos was slower and detoxification of chlorpyrifos-oxon faster in the Chinese population compared with the Caucasian population, leading to a higher chlorpyrifos sensitivity in the Caucasian population. One explanation could be that the Michaelis-Menten parameters K_M and V_{max} for the different P450 pathways were most influential in addition with physiological parameters specifically related to the liver compartment as revealed by the local sensitivity analysis. Furthermore, Zhao *et al.* (2022) extrapolated *in vitro* CYP-specific kinetic data measured as human liver microsome and Supersome™ cytochromes to the human PBK model published by Zhao *et al.* (2019). That allowed to incorporate CYP-isoform activities (*i.e.* CYP1A2, CYP2B6, CYP2C19, CYP3A4) in each biotransformation pathway to indicate the proportion of metabolites resulted from the different CYP-isoforms. This approach led to an identification of inter-individual variation in biotransformation of chlorpyrifos and its cholinesterase inhibition in blood validated against human biomonitoring data. The code was written in Berkeley Madonna and available as Supplement in Zhao *et al.* (2019).

Zhao et al. (unpublished) developed a chlorpyrifos model specifically for the quantitative *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation (QIVIVE) of developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) induced via oral exposure. Therefore, the model contains an uterus compartment, mimicking very early pregnancy (no placental barrier present yet) and describes the physiology of a woman in child bearing age. The model was also developed to perform QIVIVE for other endpoints in the future and to be able to use in combination with HBM data. As such, the model contains twelve compartments (*i.e.* brain, lung, heart, muscle, adipose tissue, uterus, richly perfused tissue, slowly perfused tissue, liver, kidney, and arterial and venous blood). All compartments are flow-limited except for the brain compartment which is modelled as permeability-limited

(representing the blood-brain barrier). The model includes the bioactive metabolite chlorpyrifos-oxon (CPO) and the often in urine found metabolite 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPy). The biotransformation of CPF to CPO and TCPy in the liver, and the biotransformation of CPO to TCPy in blood and liver was described as provided in Zhao *et al.* (2022). Other metabolites are not included in the model. The simulated time-course of TCPy in plasma correlated well with *in vivo* data from Nolan *et al.* (1984) and Smith *et al.* (2014) (based on Kisicki *et al.* (1999) and Timchalk *et al.* (2002b)). Simulated cumulative urinary excretion of TCPy correlated well with two datasets from Smith *et al.*, 2014 (based on Nolan *et al.* (1984), Kisicki *et al.* (1999) and Timchalk *et al.* (2002b)). While the dose was unknown for two intoxication cases, the plasma concentrations over time of CPF of the two individuals followed similar curves when the dose were estimated (Drevenkar *et al.*, 1993). At the time of writing, the sensitivity analysis was not performed yet. The code will be available in the supplementary materials of the published article and was coded using Berkeley Madonna.

Azinphos-methyl

For Azinphos-methyl, one of the most common insecticides used in fruit farming, PBK models have not yet published in literature. Only a very simplified toxicokinetic description with three compartments (*i.e.* absorption sites, body burden, and urine) has been developed for human health risk **assessment (Carrier & Brunet, 1999)**. In this model, alkylphosphate metabolites have been measured in human urine as an indicator for Azinphos-methyl exposure. Using the simplified toxicokinetic model, Carrier and Brunet (1999) estimated that the safe limit is reached at a cumulative 0.215 μM alkylphosphate/kg bw eliminated in urine the first 24 hours after a single exposure. Even though the used software was not stated by Carrier and Brunet (1999), model equations are provided in the main article.

2.5.2.2. Pyrethroids

Since the HBM4EU review (Brochot *et al.*, 2019b), one model for deltamethrin was published (Maass *et al.*, 2023) and briefly detailed below.

Table 8 provides a summary of inventoried PBK models for pyrethroids.

Maass *et al.* (2023) aimed to estimate human fetal brain concentration after a maternal exposure to deltamethrin (DLT). They developed a PBK model for deltamethrin (DLT) for rat and for Human including pregnancy that integrated *in vitro* results. They implemented the PBK in PK-Sim. The pregnant women model includes 22 compartments for the mother (blood, lung, stomach, small and large intestine, pancreas, spleen, portal vein, gallbladder, liver, bone, brain, fat, gonads, heart, kidneys, muscle, skin, breasts, endometrium, myometrium, placenta) and 3 for the fetuses (fetal plasma, lumped tissue compartments, placenta). Only the oral ingestion exposure route was considered. Metabolism was informed via expression of cytosolic carboxylesterases CES1 in microsomal, cytosolic, and plasma spaces, and cytochrome P450 (CYP1A2).

Table 8. Summary of PBK models for pyrethroids.

References	Compounds	Exposure routes	Biological matrix	Population
Godin <i>et al.</i> (2010)	Deltamethrin	Oral ingestion	Blood	Adults
Tornero-Velez <i>et al.</i> (2012)	Permethrin + DCCA	Oral ingestion, Dermal, inhalation	Urine	Adults
Wei <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Permethrin + 3-PBA	Oral ingestion, Dermal, inhalation	Urine	Adults
Darney <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Permethrin + DCCA	Oral ingestion, Dermal, inhalation	Urine	Adults
Quindroit <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Deltamethrin, Permethrin, Cypermethrin, Cyfluthrin + metabolites	Oral ingestion, Dermal, inhalation	Urine	Lifetime (validated for adults)
Mallick <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Deltamethrin, Permethrin, Bifenthrin, Esfenvalerate, Cyalothrin, Cyfluthrin, Cyphenothrin	Oral ingestion, Dermal	Urine	Adults and children
Maass <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Deltamethrin	Oral ingestion	Blood	Rats and Humans (pregnancy, <i>in utero</i>)

2.5.2.3. Other pesticides

From the HBM4EU review, no PBK models were found for glyphosate and DEET. However, for Fipronil, a PBK model was developed (Tonnelier *et al.*, 2012). Since the HBM4EU review, the literature search was performed on other pesticides for which PBK models are available: chlordecone, haloxyfop and epyrifenacil. Table 9 summarized recently published PBK models for these pesticides.

Cooper *et al.* (2019) developed a PBK model to assess potential crop sprayer operator exposure to the herbicide **haloxyfop**. A permeability-limited PBK model was constructed with

parameter uncertainty and variability, and the model was calibrated using a Bayesian analysis via Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods. The model contains 8 compartments (blood, lungs, skin, kidneys, spleen, liver, GIT and rest of body) and exposure can occur through the dermal and inhalation routes. Oral ingestion route is included in the model but not validated. The ADME processes are likely to influence the internal disposition of haloxyfop *in vivo*, such as liver and kidney transporter activity. The PBK model does not account for the hydrolysis of haloxyfop-methyl ester, and primarily deals with the major systemic metabolite (haloxyfop). Hepatic metabolism was modelled using first order Michaelis-Menten kinetics with enterohepatic recirculation activated for haloxyfop and its glucuronide conjugate. Although reabsorption of both compounds from the gut is modelled, hydrolysis of the glucuronide conjugate to haloxyfop is omitted due to largely unknown activity levels of β -glucuronidase produced from gut flora. HBM data of operators were used for calibration and it was assumed that: 1) the average duration of dermal exposure for operators was 108 min, 2) the body weight of each adult operator was 70 kg, 3) the total body surface area was 16,370 cm², and 4) potential exposure occurred through dermal and inhalation routes. The model code is available upon request and GNU MCSim (version 5.3) was used. This model was not evaluated or validated.

Hirasawa *et al.* (2022) developed a PBK model to evaluate human internal dosimetry of the main metabolite of **epyrifenacil**, S-3100-CA. The model includes 17 compartments (plasma, liver (intracellular), liver (interstitial), adipose, bone, brain, small intestine, heart, lung, muscle, skin, spleen, stomach, large intestine, pancreas, gonads, kidney). This PBK model was constructed using mice and its quantitative performance was validated. Regarding the parameters that might have a large effect on the prediction results in humans, they did not use a simple mouse-to-human organ weight scaling factor to extrapolate any of these parameters, because such extrapolation would have directly affected the reliability of the prediction result in humans. Consequently, they intended to obtain those human parameters precisely by employing the GUT framework and the method using chimeric mice with humanized liver. The reliability of the reported human pharmacokinetic prediction data was considered to be higher than the data predicted by the conventional methods that include simple interspecies extrapolation. A sensitivity analysis was performed and indicates that the absorption and excretion rate constant as well as the hepatic elimination intrinsic clearance of the metabolite and its fraction unbound in the liver were sensitive parameters. The model was coded with acslXtreme (version 3.0.1.6) and available in the supplementary material.

Emond and Multigner (2022) aimed to develop a PBK model for **chlordecone** and its metabolites in the rat and extrapolate it to humans based on available pharmacokinetic data in the literature. The model accounts for seven compartments: lungs, blood, brain, skin, adipose tissue, liver, and the rest of the body. Only the oral ingestion exposure route was considered for calibration, despite inhalation and dermal contact can be considered. This is the first human PBK model applied to chlordecone. This model was designed, optimized, and

assessed using all the data available in the literature for rats. The human PBK model simulations were compared to two datasets, adults from general population and workers. This model was not validated. Also, the calibration step should be refined as there was no exposure data to validate the reverse dosimetry which serves as a starting point for testing the productivity of the model. The model is coded in AcslX (version 3.1.5.1). The code is not provided, however the equations for humans are given in the supplementary material.

Table 9. Summary of recently developed PBK models for chlordecone, haloxyfop and epyrifenacil.

References	Compounds	Exposure routes	Biological matrix	Population
Cooper <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Halofyop + metabolite	(Oral ingestion), Dermal, inhalation	Blood and urine	Workers (adults)
Hirasawa <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Epyrifenacil + metabolite	Oral ingestion	Blood	Adults
Emond and Multigner (2022)	Chlordecone + metabolite	Oral ingestion (also includes dermal and inhalation but not calibrated/validated)	Blood	Adults

3. Evolution through life of toxicokinetic processes and associated parameters

3.1. Human life stage PBK models

Human life stage PBK models attempt to incorporate ‘the totality of exposures received by a person during life’, also defined as exposome (Li *et al.*, 2019). Lifelong exposure of compounds to humans may occur when the contact with the exposure source is frequent, the half-life of an accumulated compound is long, and/or the compound is very persistent. It is therefore crucial to understand the impact of chronic exposure to compounds on potential human health effects.

As a first step, a review was performed in commonly used scientific libraries (*e.g.*, Web of science, PubMed). The keywords which were used referred to the different life stages. The studies that not referred to humans were excluded. Different combinations of keywords used, including several key words, such as ‘Physiologically based pharmacokinetic (or toxicokinetic or biokinetic) model + PBPK (or PBK or PBTK or PBBK) + lifetime (or lifespan or life course) + human’.

We identified 12 main human life stage PBK models that were published between 2002 and 2021 (Table 10), with some of them already mentioned in the HBM4EU project (Sarigiannis *et al.*, 2017a). It has to be noticed that PBK models developed for specific sensitive time windows (*i.e.* fetus, infant, toddler, children, adolescents, adults, pregnant women, elderly persons) have been excluded from this literature search. Instead, we focused on PBK models that spanned over several sensitive time windows. The earliest published article by Clewell *et al.* (2002) reviewed and evaluated the potential impact of age- and gender-dependent toxicokinetic differences on tissue dosimetry as a theoretical concept. Otherwise PBK models were mathematically described by incorporating between 8 (Mallick *et al.*, 2020) and 22 compartments (Beaudouin *et al.*, 2010; Brochot & Quindroit, 2018). Most common compartments were blood plasma/serum, fat, liver, brain, gastrointestinal tract, kidney, slowly perfused compartment, and rapidly perfused compartment. The human life stage PBK models encompassed various chemical classes such as PFAS (only PFOA and PFOS), metals (only lead and cadmium), industrial chemicals (*i.e.* vinyl chloride, perchloroethylene), dioxin-like chemicals (*i.e.* 2,3,7,8-tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin and polychlorinated biphenyls), and pesticides (*i.e.* chlorpyrifos, deltamethrin).

All life stage PBK models identified (12) included age-dependent physiological changes of the human body, covering age ranges from birth up to a maximum of 90 years of age (Deepika *et al.*, 2021). Only 4 out of 12 PBK models added a fetal sub-model to the life stage PBK model and included the placenta as compartment for substance transfer between mother and fetus (Beaudouin *et al.*, 2010; El-Masri *et al.*, 2016; Sarigiannis *et al.*, 2020; Verner *et al.*, 2008). The age-dependent physiological changes were mostly modelled separately for male and female subjects except for the female-specific life stage PBK models published by Verner *et al.* (2008) and El-Masri *et al.* (2016).

Table 10. Overview of human life stage PBK models published in literature.

Reference	Compounds	Age	Number of compartments	Inter-individual variability (e.g., bodyweight)	Enzyme activity	Compared to human data
Beaudouin <i>et al.</i> , 2010	1,3-butadiene 2,3,7,8-tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin (TCDD)	0-60	22	Yes	Yes	Yes
Brochot and Quindroit, 2018	TCDD Pb PFOA PFOS	0-80	22	Yes	Yes	Yes
Clewell <i>et al.</i> , 2002	Various compounds	0-50	Qualitative discussion about ADME	No	Yes	No
Clewell <i>et al.</i> , 2004	Isopropanol Vinyl chloride Methylene chloride Perchloroethylene TCDD Nicotine	0-75	12	No	Yes	Only for Isopropanol
Deepika <i>et al.</i> , 2021	PFOS Triclosan	0-90	10	Yes	No	Yes
El-Masri <i>et al.</i> , 2016	Fluazinam Pyridaben PFOS	0-45	12	No	Yes	No
Mallick <i>et al.</i> , 2020	Deltamethrin Cis-permethrin Trans-permethrin Esfenvalerate Cyphenothrin Cyhalothrin Cyfluthrin Bifenthrin	0-25	8	Yes	Yes	No
Pendse <i>et al.</i> , 2020	Trichloroethylene ATRA Coumarin	0-60	14	Yes	Yes	No
Poet <i>et al.</i> , 2017	Chlorpyrifos	0.5-60	8	Yes	No	Yes
Sarigiannis <i>et al.</i> , 2020	Bisphenol A Bis(2-ethylhexyl) DEHP Cadmium	0-80	14	Yes	Yes	Yes
Smith <i>et al.</i> , 2014	Chlorpyrifos Chlorpyrifos-oxon (Metabolite) TCP (Metabolite)	0-80	9	No	Yes	Yes
Verner <i>et al.</i> , 2008	Hexachlorobenzene Polychlorinated biphenyl-153 Polychlorinated biphenyl-180	0-60	10	Yes	Yes	No

Human life stage PBK models have incorporated calibrated equations to account for age-dependent physiology and biochemical changes. Hereby, input parameters are modelled to be dynamic over lifetime such as body weight, organ volumes scaled according to body weight, organ-specific blood flows, fractions of binding sites, intrinsic enzyme and transporter activity, and glomerular filtration rate. Equations of age-dependent input parameters were calibrated according to openly available population data. Recently, a repository has been published that describes anatomical, physiological, and biological PBK parameters for an aging population (Stader *et al.*, 2019). It also could be noted that these life stage PBK models simulate substance exposure in an individual. However, exposure and physiological variability need to be accounted for to simulate inter-individual variability within a population. Therefore, population-based PBK model applications have been discussed and Monte Carlo simulations have been applied in seven human life stage PBK models to account for exposure variability and inter-variability in the human population (Beaudouin *et al.*, 2010; Brochot & Quindroit, 2018; Deepika *et al.*, 2021; Mallick *et al.*, 2020; Pendse *et al.*, 2020; Sarigiannis *et al.*, 2020; Verner *et al.*, 2008).

Our summary indicated that we are currently lacking human life stage PBK models that incorporate the “totality of exposures” instead of single compound exposure. Thereby, the “totality of exposures” incorporates co-exposure to multiple compounds and other factors influencing ADME processes of compounds such as food consumption and microbiota. Moreover, human life stage PBK models lack incorporating of real lifetime exposure scenarios including collected data of aggregated exposure data over long period-of-time and/or longitude human biomonitoring data. This is of importance as frequency and abundance of compound exposure may change over a lifetime. For instance, dietary habits change through life including the consumption of compounds present in food and/or drinking water (Pruvost-Couvreur *et al.*, 2020). In addition, contact to exposure sources by for instance hand-to-mouth habits may differ between age groups. Another example is that occupational exposure may change through life due to workplace changes. These examples illustrate that exposure received by a person during life is very complex and requires collected data over long period-of-time. Another limitation is the lack of harmonized and transparent models. Multiple software languages have been used to code the mathematical equations such as GNU MCSim, ACSL, MATLAB and R. Mallick *et al.* (2020) published the modelling code written in the software R, while others only described their human life stage PBK models using equations. Considering this limitation, Pendse *et al.* (2020) recently published the R package ‘PLETHEM’ that includes a generic life stage population-based PBK model.

3.2. Enzyme and transporter abundance

An important aspect of chemical risk assessment is to understand inter-individual variability in populations. Factors such as age, gender, ethnicity, genotype, and disease state may influence ADME processes, leading to differences in body burdens/organ concentrations

between individuals and, consequently, the probability to be associated with a human health effect. Differences in social behavior are additional factors that may influence the exposure frequencies and amounts between individuals. In human life stage PBK models, one major actor to consider is the variability of protein abundances depending on age, gender, ethnicity, genotype, and disease state that may modify activities of metabolizing enzymes and transporters. Therefore, the ADME mass fluxes of compounds may differ between individuals as well as subpopulations even when the individuals are exposed to the same amount of compound and time course.

Ladumor *et al.* (2019) recently published a repository of human protein abundance data of metabolizing enzymes and transporters with the aim to be used for PBK modelling approaches. Based on 18 publications, this meta-analysis provides abundance data for in total 159 proteins, consisting of 67 uptake transporters, 37 efflux transporters, 20 phase I enzymes (CYP), 14 phase II enzymes (UGTs), 11 phase II non-UGTs and 10 Phase I non-CYPs. Ladumor *et al.* (2019) only included absolute protein abundances (in pmol per mg protein unit) from individual microsomal samples quantified by LC-MS/MS or Western blotting. Another open-source tool is BRENDA (BRaunschweig ENzyme DAtabase; <https://www.brenda-enzymes.org>) that has collected more than 5 million enzyme and transporter data for 13,000 organisms since 1987 (Chang *et al.*, 2021). These data sets present the basis for *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation, till example for non-linear and substance-specific transporter-mediated hepatic and renal clearance rates and enzymatic biotransformation processes. Furthermore, scale factors for protein abundances implemented in PBK models facilitate the modeling of ADME processes for individual age groups, different genders, and sick sub-populations. In addition, it has to be noted that protein abundances vary between different individuals, tissues and laboratories and that the variabilities need to be accounted for in PBK models in the simplest way to minimize computing capacity. Therefore, it is of uttermost importance to use those data for the most influential transport -and enzyme-mediated ADME modifications only dependent on the compound.

3.3. Enzyme- and transporter-mediated ADME modifications of the prioritized compounds

In addition to the public available data sets, we searched for human protein abundance data (mean \pm standard deviation) quantified for 49 most studied enzymes and 18 transporters, with regard to compounds interactions (Evans & Relling, 1999; Guéniche *et al.*, 2020). We found protein abundances for 23 out of 49 enzymes (47%) and all transporters searched. We further researched if the prioritized chemical families (*i.e.* PFAS, bisphenols, pesticides, metals, and mycotoxins) interact with these most studied proteins, indicated by *in vitro* studies and/or implemented in PBK models. Non-linear Michaelis-Menten kinetics including the parameters' maximum reaction velocity (V_{max}) and Michaelis-Menten constant (K_M) were mostly found for the chemical groups.

We found that all PFAS (*i.e.* PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFBS, PFHxS and PFOS) are attributed to active renal tubular reabsorption via organic anion transporter (OAT) - mediated processes, while biotransformation can be neglected for those PFAS. Bisphenol A, F and S are transported by P-glycoprotein (P-gp), Breast Cancer Resistance Protein (BCRP), OAT and Organic Cation Transporter (OCT). However, we just found a limited data set of quantified Michaelis-Menten kinetics for transporter interactions with bisphenols. Interestingly, biotransformation of free forms of bisphenols are catalyzed to conjugated bisphenols (*e.g.*, glucuronidated) by Phase II enzymes in the liver (*e.g.*, UGT2A1, UGT1A9, SULT1A1). In contrast, pesticides are mainly biotransformed via Phase I CYP enzymes. We found Michaelis-Menten kinetics of CYP enzymatic reaction rates for chlorpyrifos, carbofuran and dimethoate (*e.g.*, CYP3A4, CYP2C19, CYP1A2). Transport-mediated ADME processes were not reported in literature for organophosphates. Similarly, information of Michaelis-Menten kinetics were found for pyrethroids, again for *e.g.* CYP3A4, CYP2C19, and CYP1A2. In contrast to organophosphates, the pyrethroids deltamethrin, cis-permethrin and trans-permethrin seem to inhibit the P-gp/MDR1 and NTCP membrane proteins. Mycotoxins were the least studied chemical family and we only found CYP enzymatic reaction rates for aflatoxin B1 (CYP3A4, CYP2A6, CYP2A13), while no information was found for the searched mycotoxins. For the time being, it is still not quantified how transporters interact with metals and their other forms (*e.g.*, due to methylation) causing adverse effects on human health. One of the key characteristics included in the 'metabolism' of metals is bioaccumulation as well as the short methylation pathways until clearance. Looking at the literature no incidents were found regarding interactions with specific enzymes, except iAs. New responses in these questions are originated from the application of NAMs (New Approach Methods) in toxicological sciences and public health (Varshavsky *et al.*, 2023). To conclude, transport- and enzyme-mediated proteins differently interact with chemicals leading to ADME modifications. It is still uncertain to predict differences in body burdens and/or organ concentrations depending on age, gender, ethnicity, genotype, and disease state based on human protein abundances.

4. Data gaps identified and recommendations

4.1. PBK models gaps

A summary of available PBK models in literature was performed according to the studied population, exposure routes, biological matrices used, and substance-specific parameters sources (Annex 3, an example is shown in Table 11). It was noticed that several PBK models exist for PFOA, PFOS, BPA, pyrethroids, chlorpyrifos, some mycotoxins (ZEN), cadmium and mercury. However, for lead, chromium, arsenic, bisphenols (except from BPA), PFAS (other than PFOA and PFOS), as well as for pesticides (except pyrethroids and chlorpyrifos), only a few models were developed, if any at all. The main population represented in this inventory is adults (83%, from 18 to 65 years), exposed through oral ingestion (87.5%), with blood only (28.3%) or urine only (26%) or both (45.7%) as biological matrices.

After the adults, the main represented sub-groups of population are child (25%, from 3 to 10 years), followed by infant (from birth to 1 year) and teen (19%, from 10 to 18 years), toddler (18%, from 1 to 3 years), pregnant women, *in utero* life and elderly (14%, elderly: from 65 years). Regarding exposure routes, dermal contact and inhalation exposures represent less than the half available models (41% and 33% respectively). Additionally, only 16% of the models can account for all exposure routes (aggregate exposure). New biological matrices used to quantify biomarkers such as hair or meconium were not considered in any of the listed PBK models.

To assess internal exposure during the life course, several lifetime PBK models (*i.e.* at least including childhood starting at 3 y.o to adulthood) were identified (24%): five for cadmium, two for PFAS, bisphenols, organophosphates (chlorpyrifos), and pyrethroids, as well as one for lead and chromium. For mercury, arsenic, mycotoxins and other pesticides, no lifetime model was found. In addition, PBK models simulating compound mixture interactions are largely lacking.

For **organophosphates**, PBK models were developed for two compounds: chlorpyrifos and azinphos-methyl. They were developed mainly for general and occupational adult, as well as for children. Human PBK models including pregnancy models need to be further developed for this group of pesticides, only two PBK models were developed for pregnant women exposed to chlorpyrifos (Lowe *et al.* (2009), based on Timchalk *et al.* (2002a) and Poet *et al.* (2017)). PBK models are missing for many relevant organophosphates including triazophos, dichlorvos, omethoate, formetanate, primiphos-methyl, methomyl, which all have been detected in European HBM studies. In addition, dermal and inhalation exposure routes for organophosphates are more investigated for occupational population than for general population.

For **pyrethroids**, the main elimination process for these compounds is by urinary excretion of their metabolites. Thus, urine is the main biological matrix used in HBM surveys to quantify

the metabolites, which are the biomarkers of population exposure to pyrethroids. As a metabolite is often common to several parent compounds, with a single biomarker measurement, it is not possible to identify the contribution of each parent compound. This gap could be filled in future HBM surveys. Inhalation and dermal contact exposure routes were investigated but should be refined. For example, it was found that the permethrin synergist Piperonyl Butoxide is a biomarker of inhalation exposure for general population and may impact neurodevelopment (Berger-Preiß *et al.*, 2009; Horton *et al.*, 2011). Thus, more details on the exposure routes should be investigated for pyrethroids, to refine the effects on health for sensitive population (*e.g.*, pregnant woman, *in utero* life, children).

For **other pesticides**, only adults were studied exposed via oral ingestion (100%), dermal (50%) and inhalation (25%). These models' matrices are blood (in all models) and urine (25%). Half of the models were used for workers. No PBK models has been developed for glyphosate and DEET. Additional PBK models could be developed for other pesticides that are detected in European HBM surveys if additional data are provided. Refinements can be performed on the existing models in adding other sub-group of population.

For **bisphenols**, a few models were developed for pregnant women: two models for BPA and one for BPS. Both oral ingestion and dermal contact exposure routes were accounted in PBK models. Besides, two models exist to describe BPAF and BPF exposure, while 13 PBK models were developed for BPA, indicating that further refinements on other BPA substitutes could be investigated. Moreover, developments to account for pregnancy and *in utero* life in PBK models for bisphenols are required.

Regarding to **PFAS**, several models were developed for PFOA and PFOS, while models for other PFAS should be highly investigated as a few are available. Since the latest scientific evaluation on the risks to human health related to the presence of perfluoroalkyl substances in food (EFSA, 2020), the EFSA CONTAM Panel (EFSA, 2020) decided to perform the assessment for the sum of four PFASs: PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS and PFOS. Thus, further models are required for PFHxS and PFNA to perform the assessment for these four compounds. Two and three models account for pregnancy and *in utero* life for PFOS and PFOA respectively, while no models have been developed for PFHxS or PFNA considering pregnancy. Moreover, the main exposure route considered in these PBK models were the oral ingestion, while only two models of this chemical family account for aggregate exposure (*i.e.* 13%). Further developments could be conducted to include additional exposure routes (*i.e.* inhalation and dermal contact) even if they are negligible for adults, while for other sub-group of population, such as infant or toddler, they can be of importance (*e.g.*, more dust ingestion and indoor air inhalation due to their behaviour). Also, excretion via faeces might be needed to be considered in the future.

Regarding metals, for **chromium**, dermal contact and inhalation exposure routes are not considered in the existing models. Only one model accounts for lifetime exposure but does not include pregnancy and *in utero* life.

For **arsenic** and **mercury**, only one route of exposure is considered (dermal contact for mercury and oral ingestion for arsenic). Further developments to consider at least two exposure routes should be investigated. Besides, no PBK models has been developed for childhood, and only one model accounts for pregnancy for mercury exposure.

For **cadmium**, the exposure routes by inhalation and oral ingestion were considered in the available PBK models. Additionally, no PBK model describes pregnancy or *in utero* life, while some effects are associated to pregnancy exposure to cadmium on the size at birth for example (Kippler *et al.*, 2012). Thus, a PBK model for cadmium (and other metals, *i.e.* mixtures) describing pregnancy and *in utero* life could be performed to refine risk assessment for this population.

No PBK model has been developed for pregnant women exposed to **lead**. Both inhalation and oral ingestion were considered in the models available in the literature. Further developments to account for pregnancy and *in utero* life could be performed.

For **mycotoxins**, oral ingestion is the only exposure route considered for now in PBK models. These models focus only on adults, for blood (in all models) and urine (60% of the models available). For these substances, further developments to account for additional exposure routes, such as inhalation, could be investigated in the next years of this project. Additionally, focus on occupational data could be interesting to perform risk assessment for this population (*e.g.*, occupational exposure by inhalation by grain workers).

Additionally, Annex 3 indicates that *in vivo* methods were primarily required to obtain substance-specific parameters for the prioritized compounds.

ADDITIONAL DELIVERABLE AD6.4

Table 11. Example of the summary table of available PBK models in literature for PFAS, BPs, metals, pesticides and mycotoxins. The complete file is provided in Annex 3.

chemical family	compound	Population subgroups										Exposure routes			Matrices				Chemical-specific parameters
		fetus	infant (0-1)	toddler (1-3)	child (3-10)	teen (10-18)	adult (18-65)	pregnant woman	elderly (> 65)	workers	lifetime?	inhalation	oral ingestion	dermal contact	blood (plasma, serum)	urine	hair	meconium	
PFAS	PFOA						x							x	x				x
	PFOA	x						x				x	x	x					x
	PFOS		x	x	x	x	x						x						x
	PFOS	x						x						x	x				x
Bisphenol	BPA		x	x (<2)										x					
			x	x	x (<5)									x					

4.2. Parameters gaps

These last few years, the use of NAMs (Kavlock *et al.*, 2018) is recommended in toxicological sciences and public health (Varshavsky *et al.*, 2023). The use of NAMs implies an increase of PBK modelling to improve speed of development and the scientific relevance of the models. Paini *et al.* (2019) introduced the concept of “next generation” PBK models which are developed using approaches that do not require additional animal use to generate parameterization or validation data. Thus, the parameterisation of a PBK model in development should be mainly based on NAMs such as *in vitro* and/or *in silico* data, by no longer carrying out *in vivo* data. For example, the use of *in vitro* ADME data for the parameterization of PBK models requires an *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE). IVIVE relies on an understanding of the experimental and biological factors that differ between the *in vitro* model and the *in vivo* situation and requires the use of scaling factors. Under the NAMs concept, PBK models are also of interest for their usage in interspecies extrapolations to predict an *in vivo* toxicokinetic profile in humans without performing human exposure studies. Beside the use of IVIVE PBK models, also allometric scaling is in use, considering a regression equation involving body weight to predict a parameter of interest in a different animal species, as for absorption and metabolism rates. Allometric scaling is also used to extrapolate from adult human to children for example.

4.2.1. Physiological parameters

To develop a life stage PBK model, data on physiological parameters related to each age group (*e.g.*, the population of interest: children, pregnant women, elderly) are required to inform the PBK model. To generate reliable predictions, a comprehensive description of system characteristics is essential to fully represent the population of interest. In performing this review, and as suggested for elderly population in the work of Stader *et al.* (2019), it should be necessary to have harmonized framework regarding equations related to age. For now, the gaps identified regarding physiological parameters are a lack of a clear harmonization in the system data related to age among PBK lifetime models. For example, the review on children performed by Verscheijden *et al.* (2020) highlights that paediatric PBK models could be improved by obtaining better defined physiological parameters (which implies a need for verification of models) and by filling the gap in availability and quality of systems data (*e.g.*, to assess ontogeny patterns regarding to the expression of enzymes and transporters in different organs and the interplay with other co-variates). For pregnancy, several studies have described the physiological changes described in PBK models (Abduljalil *et al.*, 2012; Dallmann *et al.*, 2018; Kapraun *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, we noted that the age-dependent physiological changes were mostly modelled separately for male and female subjects, but not considered for some compounds. Thus, a harmonization of parametrization related to age among PBK models to describe similar processes (*e.g.*, pregnancy) are needed. Besides, the variability among individuals should be considered for each age group of interest.

Regarding to protein expression levels, harmonized scaling factors for protein abundances implemented in PBK models for individual age groups, different genders, and sick sub-

populations are needed. Similar data are needed regarding to their activity, despite information on variability in activity is available for some drug-metabolising enzymes. While detailed information is mostly available for adults, other age groups data are scarcer. The use of scaling factors for age groups in the protein abundance values are pertinent (Ladumor *et al.*, 2019) and might be informed for other enzymes and transporters and then harmonized. For this step, accounting for variability (*e.g.*, due to individuals, tissues considered and measured data obtained between different laboratories) is highly recommended. For specific TK questions, it might be necessary to incorporate more detail on protein abundance for age groups, as done in the work of van Groen *et al.* (2021), which gathers ontogeny of hepatic transporters and metabolizing enzymes in humans as a first step. Despite the liver is an organ of great interest for enzymes and transporters, other tissue-specific proteins that are known to be the most influential, could be investigated (*e.g.*, enzyme and transporter abundances implied in the blood brain barrier (BBB), intestines, skin, lungs, kidney, intestinal metabolism, or placental transfer).

4.2.2. Substance-specific parameters

For substance-specific parametrization, data are required to inform on ADME process of a compound. Regarding enzymes and transporters susceptible to be impacted by the prioritized compounds, more data (*in vitro* or *in silico*) are needed for metals, organophosphates (for chlorpyrifos, carbofuran and dimethoate) and mycotoxins (except for aflatoxin B1). Additionally, more information is welcomed to quantify the interaction between transporters and bisphenols. Growing numbers of HBM surveys and computational methods (quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) or advanced algorithms) facilitate the parametrisation process for data poor compounds, especially for metabolic parameters and tissue:blood partition coefficients (Sarigiannis *et al.*, 2017b).

Regarding to non-oral exposure routes, physiological information is still complicated to obtain. There is still a need to have a better translation of *in vitro* assays data to *in vivo*. Moreover, the lack of information about metabolism and transport in the administering tissues (*i.e.* skin, lung) by dermal and inhalation exposure routes is an obstacle for their inclusion in models.

Interindividual half-life of a compound is of importance in PBK models, especially for persistent compounds. For example, the EFSA (2020) reports disparities on the half-life value of PFOS (from 1.9 to 18 years) and PFOA (from 1.2 to 8.5 years). Refinements on this substance-specific parameter will improve the risk assessment, especially for the early life exposure.

Partition coefficients are also important parameters which are compound specific. Missing information was highlighted for the *in utero* life. Most often, it is hypothesized that fetal partition coefficients are similar as adults, or similar to those of fetal animals including extrapolation to humans. However, it was shown that this hypothesis may not be assumed for some chemical family, such as for PFAS (Mamsen *et al.*, 2019). For these parameters, more information is required for the *in utero* life stage, especially for blood and brain. However, for now, the method illustrated in the recent study of Kapraun *et al.* (2022) could be used to

parametrized the partition coefficients using the R package 'httk' to attribute different values for mother and for fetuses.

The PBK models inventory also highlighted the fact that placental transfer, intestinal and BBB or other crucial biological processes relative to membrane transporters were rarely considered in PBK models. Including these specific processes allows to refine the link between exposure and effects, such as effects on neurodevelopment (Murata *et al.*, 2022). Further data on the BBB should be particularly investigated as neurodevelopmental tests may be used in association of biomarker levels to assess effects on neurodevelopment in HBM surveys (*e.g.*, for metals, pyrethroids or bisphenols). Additionally, incorporation of more data for endocrine regulation should be investigated (Couderq *et al.*, 2020) especially concerning pesticides (organophosphates and pyrethroids) associated with brain endpoints (Leemans *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, PBK models generally successfully predict TK of a compound in pregnant women, the confidence in predicting fetal TK is limited because many parameters affecting placental compound transfer have not been mechanistically accounted for, as it is observed for drugs (Liu *et al.*, 2021). Further studies are needed to describe the mechanistic maternal-fetal compound transfer.

4.3. Recommendation to fill the gaps

To fill the gaps, several actions could be carried out by modellers and experimenters, in particular within the framework of this PARC project (WP5 and WP6). A close communication between these two spheres will be necessary to move forward in the use of NAMs. Below are discussed some suggestions to fill the identified gaps.

Regarding to PBK models that are missing for the compounds of interest, PBK models can be developed. For their parametrization, especially for substance-specific parameters, the use of analogues to fill data gaps by read-across approaches could be a way forward, as well as using QSAR models. For the existing models in the scientific literature, additional exposure routes can be added to refine the model, and in accounting for different subgroups of population. An inventory of physiological and biochemical processes at different ages is needed to prioritize and harmonize these related parameters and equations among models. Obtaining accurate and up-to-date parameter values and the relative equations for different life stages is crucial for a model to provide reliable predictions through life.

Regarding to protein abundances for human life stage PBK models, the next steps could be to focus on the incorporation of scaling factors to apply for relevant substance-specific transportation (passive diffusion, facilitated or active transport) and biotransformation, depending on the compound considered. Nowadays, PBK models typically account for metabolic pathways in a simplified way. To improve the accuracy of the models and to establish a more reliable link to the effects, it is recommended to incorporate more complex metabolic pathways, including alternative pathways and feedback mechanisms. To this end, it might be recommended to use more comprehensive data sources, such as data on the expression of metabolizing enzymes and transporters in different tissues to better describe

the distribution and metabolism of compounds in the body. Besides, for non-adult life stage, the use of scale factors in enzyme and transporters need to be incorporated in lifetime PBK models.

The impact of the human microbiome on the metabolism of xenobiotics is another apparent knowledge gap. The human situation is characterized by a large inter-individual variability in the abundance of bacteria in the large and small intestine, being for example dependent on life stage but also factors like dietary habitudes. NAM based approaches will be investigated in WP5 case studies.

For non-oral routes of exposure, further research is needed to improve the translation of *in vitro* ADME assays and their data to *in vivo*, and then to incorporate this in PBK models. For the respiratory tract, this knowledge gap is addressed in WP5 case studies.

Refinements for substance-specific parameters are needed (*e.g.*, partition coefficients, half-life, etc.), especially for the fetus and early life. Both *in vitro* and *in silico* approaches should be considered to obtain the parameters values for the prioritized compounds of interest. The use of *in silico* tools may be considered a valuable and robust approach. For example, the great number and variety of pesticides which have to be evaluated precludes the use of cost-effective and labour-consuming classical TK *in vitro* or *in vivo* methods (Chedik *et al.*, 2017), adding to the fact that TK studies in human subjects with pesticides are now hampered by appropriate ethical considerations.

Besides, PBK models often assume that all individuals have the same physiological parameters. However, significant inter-individual variability can exist in the parameters, such as metabolism rates, body weight, and organ volumes. Today, to account this variability, a factor of 10 is applied on parameters. At a low-tier testing and assessment approach, the current factor 10 could be used to incorporate the inter-individual variability. To improve PBK models accuracy and reliability, at a high-tier level, individual scenario could be incorporated (*e.g.*, information available in questionnaires from HBM data).

5. Perspectives

5.1. Perspective on use of PBK models in risk assessment

The use of NAMs in chemical risk assessment incorporates PBK models, an emerging tool that plays a crucial role for the next generation risk assessment (Pallocca *et al.*, 2022). In this framework of 3R implementation (reduce, reuse and recycle), the use of animals to obtain data tends to be reduced. PBK models can be useful to go in this direction by predicting the kinetic of a compound into the organism in requiring a limited *in vivo* data (most often already published). PBK models can be used in species extrapolation including across age groups for a specie, as well as to perform *in vitro*-to-*in vivo* extrapolations (IVIVE). PBK models are also used in the development of compound specific adjustment factors (Bhat *et al.*, 2017), in the use of biomonitoring data to estimate external exposure levels (*i.e.* reverse dosimetry, Sarigiannis *et al.* (2019)) or to derive human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs, Ougier *et al.* (2021)).

The OECD guideline 331 (OECD, 2021) on the characterisation, validation and reporting of PBK models for regulatory purposes has a dedicated section on the PBK model for risk assessment. In particular, PBK models are expected to play a critical role in converting *in vitro* concentrations that elicit cellular/sub-cellular responses (an *in vitro* PoD) to the corresponding *in vivo* external doses that results in a simulated unbound concentration at the toxicological target site for comparing with the known exposure levels in a population (QIVIVE). PBK models are also expected in Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) to make better use of existing toxicity data and inform testing needs (Sachana *et al.*, 2019). Further directions are needed to approve PBK models for compounds that do not have enough *in vivo* kinetic data for model calibration and validation. The level of confidence required for a PBK model will depend on the regulatory context of use that are determined by the regulatory assessors.

Paini *et al.* (2019) mentioned three factors that will facilitate the use of PBK modelling in regulatory decision- making: dialogue and communication, training and guidance. They also mentioned a need for a public repository for PBK models that have been peer reviewed that could be used for example for training purposes. In this objective, and under the FAIR and 3R principles, the PBK models developed or refined in PARC will be implemented in a platform (Link with WP7 and 8, in particular the Task 8.3). Najjar *et al.* (2022) suggest to, as illustrated in the Figure 1, (1) define context and implementation, taking into consideration model complexity for building fit-for-purpose PBK models, (2) harmonise physiological input parameters and their distribution and define criteria for quality substance-specific parameters, especially in the absence of *in vivo* data, (3) apply Good Modelling Practices (GMP) and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles to achieve transparency and design a stepwise approach for PBK model development for risk assessors, (4) evaluate model predictions using alternatives to *in vivo* toxicokinetic data including read-

across approaches, (5) use case studies to facilitate discussions between modellers and regulators of chemical risk assessment.

Figure 1. Suggested actions by Najjar et al. 2022 to improve the regulatory acceptance of PBK models and links with the work packages (WPs) in the framework of PARC.

Regarding to the input parameters, the authors highlighted the importance to harmonise physiological and anatomical parameters for a specific context of use and an organism, as well to account for the inter-individual variability and the range of the influential physiological and anatomical parameters. They also point out that further case studies are required to gain confidence in using PBK modelling for risk assessment (this point will be in collaboration with the WP4).

Several developments in the innovation (or next generation) of risk assessment require increased abilities to link external and internal exposures:

- Going beyond the traditional single-route exposure models, such as dietary exposure models or dermal application models, the development and increased use of aggregate exposure models require conversion of external doses in multiple sources to an aggregated internal dose.
- The increased availability and use of HBM data leads to questions about how external toxicological guidance values (GVs), *e.g.*, for dietary exposures, can be translated to equivalent guidance values (HBM-GVs) in the biological matrix of HBM, *e.g.*, blood or urine.
- In addition, PBK models coupled with exposure models and exposure reconstruction algorithms, are able to deliver external exposure estimates, that are directly used for Risk Characterization against existing external reference levels (*e.g.*, TDI, RfD, RfC)
- The increased availability and use of NAMs, such as *in vitro* methods applied to *ex vivo* tissues (*e.g.*, human hepatocyte cells) brings the possibility to derive toxicological limit

values assumed to be valid at the internal level (*e.g.*, the liver). Reverse dosimetry methods are then required to convert such results to equivalent external limit values.

- Given the lack of sufficient fully parameterised PBK model instances for compounds that are potentially toxic and relevant for regulatory risk assessment (*e.g.*, PFAS, bisphenols, metals), there is a regulatory need to apply PBK models in a flexible framework with lower tiers (such as the use of simple absorption or exposure factors, *e.g.*, the fraction urine excretion), intermediate tiers (such as generic models using QSAR parametrisation, or read-across of parameters within compound groups) and higher tiers (specifically developed and parametrised PBK models for single compound or groups of compounds, including metabolites).
- There is an increased awareness of the importance to adjust human health risk assessment conclusions considering the variability in human populations and uncertainties about data and models used. This applies as well to any conversion between external and internal exposures that is part of such risk assessments.

From these developments, it becomes obvious that integration of PBK models in a larger risk assessment framework is needed. PARC task 8.3 develops an integrative model network that will allow regulatory users as well as scientists to perform risk assessment calculations that also may involve the use of PBK models. In the development of this network, useful models and tools across PARC are identified. In cross-WP and cross-project collaborations, useful models will be integrated in the PARC model network. For PBK models, use was made of existing model links developed in previous projects namely EuroMix (MCRA) and HBM4EU (INTEGRA). The EuroMix link has integrated a generic PBK model in the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) toolbox (Tebby *et al.*, 2020; van der Voet *et al.*, 2020). MCRA will be further developed to become part of the PARC integrative model network. The toolbox can estimate dietary exposures following the detailed regulatory methods adopted by EFSA and the European Commission for mixture risk assessment of pesticides (van Klaveren *et al.*, 2019a, 2019b). It can aggregate dietary and non-dietary exposures accounting for variability and uncertainty and using either simple absorption factors or selected PBK models. At the hazard side, the toolbox contains functionality to perform dose-response modelling on *in vitro* data and convert these to external hazard characterisations using reverse dosimetry. MCRA has a procedure to integrate further PBK models when needed. The generic PBK model developed in INTEGRA (which will also be part of the PARC model network) is designed to describe as much as possible detail the ADME processes occurring in the human body at different life stages, so as to be easily applicable to a broad variety of compounds after proper parameterization. The model in its generic form includes the parent compound and up to three generations of potential metabolites. INTEGRA also describes mother fetus interactions by modelling the intra-placental properties that govern the transfer of xenobiotics and their metabolites from the mother to the fetus as it grows. The

anthropometric parameters of the models are time dependent, so as to provide a lifetime internal dose assessment, as well as to describe the continuously changing physiology of the mother and the developing fetus.

Currently, both MCRA, INTEGRA and the wider PARC integrative model network are being optimised to extend modelling abilities, such as PBK models with metabolites, substance-dependent selection of PBK models in mixture risk assessments, and distinctions between population groups (*e.g.*, general, worker) and specific age-groups within the population. Finally, in the PARC model network, semantic modelling will be used to create dictionaries of terms for *e.g.*, sources, routes, compartments and biological matrices, with the aim to get a common and interoperable use of terms and data formats for exchange between models.

The long-term perspective of the PARC integrative model network, including PBK models, is that scientists can test their proposed models and model instances in a realistic setting of risk assessment. The platform can also be used to share models and parameterisations, either publicly or in a restricted user group. The platform will include online documentation of the models that are included. On the road to regulatory acceptance, the platform will allow to create demonstrators, which are pre-set examples of calculations that can be used in collaborations with stakeholders and in trainings.

5.2. Next steps

The next steps will focus mainly on the development and/or refinement of PBK models to fill the identified gaps, as in adding other exposure routes (including aggregate exposure), and accounting for different age groups. In particular, the next steps will therefore focus on human life stage PBK models in harmonizing the equations and physiological parameters relative to age groups, and in a second step to incorporate scaling factors of human protein abundances that are relevant for substance-specific transportation and biotransformation. In parallel, to support the use of PBK models in risk assessment, several case studies will be considered. As suggestions, Table 12 and Table 13 present the next steps that may be planned in this project to refine PBK models and parametrization.

Moreover, probabilistic statistical methods will be developed (*e.g.*, Monte Carlo simulations) to improve the methodology currently used (deterministic simulation) to account for human variability and model uncertainties. New exposure index might be defined for single compounds and mixtures to reflect the variety of exposures occurring during lifetime, the occurrence and duration of exposures, the sensitivity of the life period, and the site of toxicity (target organs). Exposure scenarios will be derived by activity 6.2.1, and the simulations of the concentration of active substance(s) in target tissue(s) might be coupled to adverse outcome pathways (AOPs, in WP5) and IATA (task 6.1). The reconstructed exposure from HBM data will serve mixture risk assessment of activity 6.2.3.

Table 12. Summary of the suggested developments/refinements to fill some identified PBK model gaps.

Chemical family	Population	Exposure route	Biological matrix	Mixture development
Mycotoxins	Workers	Inhalation, ingestion	Blood	Yes
Bisphenols (e.g., BPS, BPF)	Pregnancy	Ingestion	Blood	No
Metals	Pregnancy, child, lifetime	Aggregate	Blood, urine	Yes
PFAS (e.g., PFHxS, PFNA, PFOA, PFOS)	Workers, pregnancy, child	Aggregate	Blood, urine	Yes
Organophosphates, pyrethroids	Workers, pregnancy, child	Aggregate, inhalation	Blood, urine	Yes

Table 13. Suggested processes that will be developed or refined to fill some identified substance-specific parameter gaps. BBB stands for blood-brain barrier and omics include enzymes and transporters.

Chemical family	BBB	Placental transfer	Omics	Other
Mycotoxins		Will be discussed in working groups		
Bisphenols	Yes			
Metals	Yes		Bones ossification	
PFAS				
Pyrethroids				

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Appendices

Annex 1. Inventory of PBK models.

Annex 2. Roadmaps for PBK model refinement.

Annex 3. Data gaps summary file.

The appendices are available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10013279>.